

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF REHEAT HYDROGEN FLAMES IN THE SEQUENTIAL-COMBUSTION STAGE OF A HEAVY-DUTY GAS TURBINE

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ABSTRACT

Recent theoretical studies and experimental evidence suggest that turbulent burning-rate augmentation, flame instabilities and NO_x emissions, notoriously characterizing fuel-lean hydrogen premixed combustion, are significantly mitigated at reheat combustion conditions. This is due to the favorable effects of high reactants temperature in reducing the strength of thermo-diffusive instabilities that occur in hydrogen premixed combustion with augmented severity for increasing pressure and flame temperature. In this context, Ansaldo's Constant Pressure Sequential Combustion (CPSC) system appears as an attractive approach to enable hydrogen firing of gas turbines that target high flame temperatures to retain high cycle efficiency. The present numerical modelling effort represents the first attempt to perform high-resolution Large-Eddy Simulation (LES), featuring detailed chemical kinetics and a fully compressible representation of the reactive flow, of hydrogen reheat combustion in a full-scale industrial combustor geometry with realistic geometrical features. Building upon earlier numerical modelling efforts that were limited to generic and geometrically simplified configurations with idealized reactants mixing conditions (GT2022-83218) [1], the ability of the turbulent combustion model to predict injection of the hydrogen fuel, mixing with the vitiated oxidizer stream and

spontaneous ignition of the reactants mixture at the expected stabilization location is verified. Low and high flame-temperature conditions for 100% hydrogen-firing of the engine are simulated confirming that the numerical results are in accordance with the expected flame stabilization behavior observed in test-rig experiments. Furthermore, an analysis of the hydrogen premixed flame structure at reheat combustion conditions is provided highlighting the differences observed at various locations within the combustion chamber.

Nomenclature

Abbreviations

CPSC	Constant pressure sequential combustion
DAM	Dilution-Air Mixer
DNS	Direct Numerical Simulation
LES	Large Eddy Simulation
LMA	Localized Mean Age-of-Air
MBFS	Multi-Burner First Stage
PaSR	Partially-Stirred Reactor
URANS	Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes

Greek

κ	Reaction rate correction factor due to turbulence-chemistry interaction
ϕ	Equivalence ratio

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τ_c	Chemical time scale
τ_{mix}	Turbulence mixing time scale
Roman	
C_{mix}	Tuning parameter in turbulence-chemistry interaction model
Pe	Peclet number
t_{res}^{CZ1}	Combustion Zone I residence time
t_{res}^{mix}	Mixing duct residence time
t_{res}^{out}	Global residence time
T_0	Reactant temperature
T_a	Adiabatic flame temperature
T_w	Wall temperature
t_{ign}	Ignition delay time
Y_i	Mass fraction of species i
Ze	Zeldovich number

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasingly evident need to stabilize complex future energy systems that will be dominated by an ever larger share of unsteady and non-dispatchable renewable energy sources (wind, sun), jointly with more stringent regulations on emissions of greenhouse gases and atmospheric pollutants, is motivating a gradual transition to carbon-free chemical energy vectors, such as hydrogen, for large-scale power generation [2]. When used as gas-turbine fuel, hydrogen can provide a carbon-free route to fast and reliable on-demand power generation at the scale required to stabilize the electric grid. However, due to their high reactivity, hydrogen-containing fuel blends can cause severe issues in gas-turbine burners [3] and significant challenges in simultaneously achieving low NO_x emissions performance as well as static and dynamic flame stability (i.e., avoiding flashback [4, 5, 6, 7] and thermo-acoustics instabilities [8]).

The practical issues with flame stability and emissions observed in gas-turbine burners originate from the fundamental fact that hydrogen is a unique fuel because of its high specific energy and its fast molecular diffusion relative to the diffusion of heat, resulting in a Lewis number well below unity ($Le_{H_2} \sim 0.3$) [9, 10, 11]. The low Lewis number leads to fuel-lean premixed hydrogen-air flames becoming thermo-diffusively unstable [12, 13], resulting in localized enrichment of portion of the flame front and superadiabatic conditions, ultimately leading to significant global acceleration of the flame front and NO_x emissions greatly exceeding the values expected from nominal flame properties [14].

A recent theoretical study, utilizing high-resolution Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS), has proposed a novel and more accurate scaling law, based on the ratio of opportunely-defined Zeldovich (Ze) and Peclet (Pe) numbers, for the turbulent burning rate of hydrogen-enriched flames [15]. A follow-up and ongoing study, based on several large experimental databases, confirms these theoretical findings [16]. The above mentioned Ze/Pe scal-

ing provides a theoretical foundation for the common observation that high-pressure conditions (by increasing Ze and reducing Pe), typically present in gas-turbine combustors, significantly strengthen thermo-diffusive instabilities of hydrogen flames and, consequently, the related and undesired effects on flame stability and NO_x emissions. However, the same theoretical arguments also suggest that the strength of these thermo-diffusive instabilities is reduced for increasingly high reactants temperature, resulting in lower Ze and higher Pe , i.e., for flames that are autoignition stabilized. This is graphically illustrated in Fig. 1 where the red and blue arrows present qualitative trends in the flame surface-normalized turbulent burning rate I_0 (the stretch factor [17]) as function of the Ze/Pe scaling parameter.

FIG. 1: STRETCH FACTOR I_0 VS. Ze/Pe COLORED BY THE PRESSURE LEVEL.

The practical consequences of the above theoretical considerations, relevant to gas-turbine applications, is that the principal undesired effects of thermo-diffusive instabilities on hydrogen premixed combustion are greatly mitigated in autoignition-stabilized systems. This conclusion confirms empirical observations about the ability of reheat (autoignition-stabilized) combustion systems, as deployed in Ansaldo Energia GT36 [18], to operate on high fractions of hydrogen (~ 70 vol%) without compromising on the demanding H-class firing temperatures [19]. The *sequential combustor* concept, first implemented in Alstom's GT24/GT26 gas turbines [21] and further developed by Ansaldo Energia. Ansaldo Energia's Constant Pressure Sequential Combustor (CPSC) [18], which represents another reheat technology advancement, is integrated into the H-class GT36 engine. The system consists of two premixed combustion stages that are arranged in sequence, where flame stabilization in the first stage is classically controlled by turbulent flame propagation and in

FIG. 2: SCHEMATICS OF THE CONSTANT PRESSURE SEQUENTIAL COMBUSTOR (CPSC) FROM [20].

the second stage by autoignition due to the high temperature of the combustion products from the first stage. A cross section of the CPSC is illustrated in Fig. 2 where the green rectangle highlights the position, within the CPSC, of the autoignition-stabilized second-stage burner, described in the following as Center Body Burner (CBB) [22], and the subject of the present work.

The first stage is aerodynamically stabilized by vortex breakdown and flame propagation, at moderate flame temperatures and therefore favourable conditions for hydrogen flames. The second stage is stabilized primarily by autoignition at even more favourable conditions that reduce the strength of the above mentioned instabilities. Although the *sequential combustor* concept was historically mostly exploited to provide operational and load-flexibility, as well as increased efficiency, the above theoretical considerations [15] and, more importantly, empirical evidence [19] suggest that the same concept is also able to provide fuel-flexibility, being capable of handling fuels with largely different reactivity spanning from natural gas to hydrogen. In its latest developments fuels with reduced reactivity, such as ammonia, are considered as well [23]. This is achieved by varying the loading of each combustor stage separately: for highly reactive fuels such as hydrogen, the first-stage combustor can operate stably at a lower flame temperature compared to standard natural gas operation. This in turn reduces the inlet temperature to the second stage sequential combustor, which counteracts the fuel reactivity effect on the auto-ignition delay time [21]. By shifting the fuel from the first to the second stage high hydrogen fuel content can be burned without de-rating the engine, i.e. without efficiency and power losses which pose a significant advantage when compared to single stage combustor, as discussed in [19, 22, 24, 25, 26, 27].

In the present work, building upon an earlier study based on greatly simplified burner geometries and idealized homogeneous fuel-oxidizer mixing assumptions [1], we perform three-

dimensional Large-Eddy Simulations (LES) with detailed chemical kinetics to predict stabilization of hydrogen flames at reheat combustion conditions in a realistic CBB geometry. The combustion system considered in the present numerical simulations has been developed for natural gas and no special tuning or modifications of its original design in respect to operation with pure hydrogen are implemented. Accordingly, an optimal behavior of the present combustion system when fired with 100% hydrogen cannot be expected and crucial enhancements of its design in this respect are under development to further improve upon the current status. Here, the aim is to assess the ability of the numerical modelling approach, applied to the present natural-gas version of the CBB geometry, to represent:

1. The process of hydrogen-fuel injection that takes place in an in-line jet configuration.
2. The three-streams mixing process between the injected hydrogen fuel, the shielding air and the hot gas emerging from the interaction between the Multi-Burner First Stage (MBFS) and the Dilution-Air Mixer (DAM), not represented in the computational domain.
3. The stabilization of the hydrogen reheat flame in the combustion chamber at low firing-temperature conditions.
4. The influence of higher firing temperature on the flame morphology and anchoring.

To minimize computational cost, only 1/12 (30°) of the actual cylindrical CPSC can geometry is represented in the computational domain. This is also limited, in the longitudinal direction, to the downstream CBB section marked by the green rectangle in Fig. 2. Considering such 30° azimuthal sector of the CBB, shown in Fig. 3, provides rotational symmetry in respect to the fuel injectors and mixing duct, thereby allowing a realistic representation of the turbulent reactive flows that takes place in the CBB. Section 2 provides a description of the numerical modelling approach, LES results spanning low to high firing-temperature conditions of the CBB are illustrated and discussed in Sec. 3. Finally, Sec. 4 summarizes our conclusions and suggestions for further work.

2 NUMERICAL MODEL AND CONFIGURATION

In the present section, the main features of the numerical tool and of the chosen mathematical modelling approach are summarized first. Then, the specific computational configuration and boundary conditions used to numerically simulate stabilization of the hydrogen reheat flames in the CBB are described.

2.1 Numerical solver

The open source set of C++ libraries OpenFOAM (version 2112), providing a generic framework for finite-volume discretization of partial differential equations, is employed in the

present study. Its object-oriented structure allows for close top-level representation of the mathematical formulations, enabling intuitive custom developments and modifications [28]. Similarly to the precursor study based on simplified assumptions [1], we have identified the standard OpenFOAM solver “reactingFoam” as a good starting point to solve the turbulent reactive flow of interest. The “reactingFoam” solver is a reactive compressible solver, a key feature for accurate prediction of the intrinsic instabilities that characterize hydrogen reheat flames at certain conditions [29]. The PIMPLE algorithm, a hybrid SIMPLE-PISO iteration scheme, is used for pressure-velocity coupling allowing larger time steps (where an adaptive time step can be used, limited by the user-specified Courant number ~ 0.8). Time integration is performed by an implicit first order Euler scheme. Interpolation of the face fluxes to the cell values is achieved by combinations of second order central differencing schemes.

Non-reactive Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) calculations utilizing the $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model are performed in order to initialize the flow before transitioning to the LES turbulence model and finally to the reactive calculations, utilizing the Partially-Stirred Reactor (PaSR) model in combination with LES. The dynamic one equation eddy viscosity model *dynamicKEqn* is employed to solve a transport equation for the subgrid-scale turbulent kinetic energy with dynamic model coefficients. The model coefficients are dynamically computed from the velocity field, and follow the framework presented in the work of Kim et al. [30]. A 9-species and 21-reactions chemical kinetics scheme is selected to represent the hydrogen combustion process [31] while the sub-grid turbulence-chemistry interactions are modelled with the PaSR model where the chemical reactions are assumed to take place in topologically complex fine structures forming a fraction of the volume in a given computational cell [32]. The reaction rate for each elementary reaction is then scaled by a correction factor κ representing the turbulence-chemistry interaction. In PaSR this correction factor is estimated as:

$$\kappa = \frac{\tau_c}{\tau_c + C_{mix}\tau_{mix}} \quad (1)$$

where τ_c is an estimated chemical time scale and τ_{mix} is an estimated turbulent mixing time scale. The chemical time scale is estimated from the elementary reaction rates in the chemical mechanism while the turbulent mixing time scale is estimated based on characteristic turbulence quantities [32]. C_{mix} is a dimensionless tuning coefficient, where $C_{mix} = 1$ for laminar flows and $0 < C_{mix} < 1$ for turbulent flows, that can be used to modulate the burning rate predicted by the PaSR model. A comprehensive sensitivity study on the value of the mixing model coefficient C_{mix} was performed by varying its value between 0.5 and 0.01 in the precursor study [1], revealing relatively minor effects on the LES solutions. Following earlier numerical modelling work

on turbulent flames at gas-turbine conditions [1, 33, 23] and considering that the reactive flows simulated in the present study are highly turbulent, featuring a bulk-flow Reynolds number ~ 2.1 million upstream of the flame at 25 bar, it is set to $C_{mix} = 0.01$ in all LES calculations. Earlier studies have also explored the relative importance of the chemical time scale τ_c vs the turbulent mixing time scale τ_{mix} in similar turbulent reactive flow configurations and concluded that the value of C_{mix} plays a secondary role due to the small relative size of the turbulent mixing time scale compared to the chemistry one that, accordingly, controls the turbulent burning rate to a leading order [1, 33, 23]. Before concluding the present section it is important to note that the same approach to turbulent combustion modelling, based on a combination of LES and PaSR, has been successfully applied in the past to reactive flows controlled by spontaneous ignition [34].

2.2 Computational configuration and boundary conditions

Figure 3 provides a qualitative representation the computational configuration considered in the present study. The hot-gas flow, emerging from the interaction between the MBFS combustion chamber and the DAM section (not represented in the simulated configuration), enters the computational domain from the left-hand side in correspondence with the boundary marked as “Dilution-Air Mixer Exit” in the figure (yellow label) and flows towards the right in the x direction. The hot-gas flow is then deflected outward, in the y direction, and away from the CPSC-can symmetry axis towards the fuel injectors. The hydrogen fuel stream, shrouded by an appropriate mass flow of shielding compressor air, is in-line injected into the hot-gas flow and mixes with it in the region denoted as Mixing Duct (blue label). Ideally, the hydrogen reheat flame is stabilized at its design location, determined by the mixing, ignition and residence time scale within the mixing duct, downstream of the sudden area change in correspondence of the region denoted as Combustion Zone I (orange label). Secondary compressor air is injected from the front panel that delimits the combustion chamber directly into the outermost region of the Combustion Zone I. Further downstream, Combustion Zone II and III (orange labels) are included in the computational domain to enable detailed insight of the entire transient ignition process that, for autoignition-stabilized flames, typically starts at downstream locations and proceeds upstream as the solution is advanced in time.

Notably, the size of the computational domain considered in the present numerical study and shown in Fig. 3 is original size as in the GT36 engine to provide a realistic representation of the time scales characterizing the reheat combustion process. A mainly hexahedral mesh, created using the *OpenFOAM* tool *snappyHexMesh*, is used in the LES calculations with tetrahedral elements present only in the near-wall regions for geometrical compliance with curved boundaries. The bulk spatial resolution

FIG. 3: 30-DEGREES AZIMUTHAL SECTOR OF THE CENTER-BODY BURNER (CBB) AND MESH RESOLUTION USED IN THE DIFFERENT REGIONS.

varies between the different regions of the computational domain as illustrated in Fig. 3 with the coarsest resolutions characterizing the most upstream and downstream regions at $\Delta s \sim 400 - 800 \mu m$ and the finest resolutions characterizing the central mixing and flame-stabilization regions at $\Delta s \sim 100 - 200 \mu m$. These spatial resolutions represent a compromise between what is practically affordable on a computational domain of such large size, compliance with standard guidelines for spatial-resolution requirements in LES models (Pope's criterion) and guidelines obtained from the precursor study about spatial-resolution requirements for hydrogen reheat flames at similar high-pressure conditions [1]. The computational mesh consists of 578, 196, 237 cells in total and the calculations are conducted in parallel on 6400 processor cores after domain decomposition by the "scotch" algorithm. The time step for the present LES calculations is limited to values between $\Delta t \sim 10 ns$ and $\Delta t \sim 100 ns$, depending on the hydrogen mass flow at the injectors, by the user-controlled condition on the Courant number ~ 0.8 and by the co-location of extremely high flow velocities and fine spatial resolution ($\Delta s \sim 100 \mu m$) within the injector nozzles. Ultimately, this results in a mean computational cost of 0.6 million core-hours per millisecond of simulated time. The residence time t_{res} of an arbitrary fluid parcel flowing in the computational domain is estimated using the Localized Mean Age-of-Air (LMA) transported scalar, as reported in earlier work [33]. For the low temperature-firing conditions, the cross sectional area-averaged value of the residence time, representing its global value, is approximately equal to $t_{res}^{out} \sim 2.5 ms$ at the downstream outlet of the computational domain while its value decreases during the transient to the higher temperature-firing conditions. This implies a mean computational cost of 1.5 million core-hours per global residence time t_{res}^{out} .

All gas inlets for the hot gas, shielding air, hydrogen fuel

and secondary air are specified as constant mass flows. The inflow and outflow pressure boundary conditions are imposed as quasi zero-gradient (fixedFluxPressure) inlet and quasi non-reflecting (waveTransmissive) outlet, similarly to the Navier-Stokes characteristic boundary condition (NSCBC) method described by [35]. A periodic (cyclic) boundary condition is imposed in the z (azimuthal) direction. All wall boundaries are set to no-slip and maintained at a constant temperature T_w^{ca} , corresponding to the compressor air temperature, in order to account for the effect of effusion wall cooling on the reactants flow, and thereby on the flame stabilization mechanism. The only exception being the temperature of the fuel-injector inner wall T_w^{fi} that is set to the fuel temperature.

The hydrogen-fuel mass flow is varied between low- and high firing-temperature conditions for the GT36. According to empirical observations, it is expected that a hydrogen reheat flame can be stabilized at the low firing-temperature conditions while transitioning to the high firing-temperature conditions would eventually lead to upstream flame displacement and off-design flame behaviour. The pressure is set to a value above 20 bar for all calculations and it is kept unchanged when transitioning from low to high firing-temperature conditions.

A rather lengthy procedure, consisting of a number of successive steps, has been developed to perform the LES calculations with the LES model described above. Firstly, a non-reactive turbulent flow field is established using a standard URANS model formulation that is then transitioned to an LES model representation of the same non-reacting flow field. The amount of hydrogen fuel introduced in the non-reactive turbulent flow field corresponds to the low firing-temperature conditions. Secondly, chemical reactions are activated and the solution is advanced in time until spontaneous ignition takes place, typically in Com-

bustion Zone II or III, on a time scale approximately equal to the nominal ignition delay time t_{ign} of the target reactive mixture. Thirdly, subsequent upstream displacement of the reaction front takes place and the solution is further advanced in time until statistically steady-state flame stabilization in Combustion Zone I (in correspondence of the cross-sectional area change) is achieved at low firing-temperature conditions. This unsteady process takes place over a time period approximately equal to 3 global residence times t_{res}^{out} and, thereafter, the statistically steady-state solution is sampled over a total of 7 global residence times t_{res}^{out} collecting 180 samples of the LES solution. Estimating the mean residence time within the area of interest of the CBB, i.e. mixing duct t_{res}^{mix} and Combustion Zone I t_{res}^{CZ1} , as $t_{res}^{CBB} \sim t_{res}^{mix} + t_{res}^{CZ1}$ it is noted that the above-mentioned 180 samples are temporally distributed with a satisfactory frequency of 10 samples per CBB residence time t_{res}^{CBB} . Finally, the hydrogen-fuel mass flow is increased from low to high firing-temperature conditions in three successive steps consisting of fuel mass-flow increments approximately corresponding to $1 \times t_{res}^{CBB}$, with intervals of $2 \times t_{res}^{CBB}$. This procedure results in a total transition time from low to high firing-temperature conditions of $7 \times t_{res}^{CBB}$. A significantly more rapid transition from low to high firing-temperature conditions, conducted over a short time interval of $1 \times t_{res}^{CBB}$, was also attempted and resulted in the abrupt and violent spontaneous ignition of a large parcel of reactants, leading to numerical issues that the solver was not able to handle. Note that even the currently used method to transition from low to high firing-temperature conditions is orders of magnitude faster than a realistic load transition, which can be implemented in a real gas turbine combustor. Thus, the numerical issues observed for the rapid transition attempted in the present numerical simulations are irrelevant to real gas turbines.

3 RESULTS

Given the size, operating conditions and complexity of the combustion system considered in the present study it is obviously unrealistic to obtain detailed flow, mixing and flame measurements useful for model validation as those that could be sampled, for example, in the case of optically accessible atmospheric flames stabilized in lab-scale burners. Therefore, the interpretation of the present LES results is not based on a detailed comparison with spatially-resolved flame data but it uniquely relies on the empirically-observed global behavior of the combustion system at similar firing conditions [19]. Ultimately, the computational setup used in the present study and its related outcome contribute to an improved understanding of the model's ability to represent hydrogen reheat combustion at gas turbine conditions and are of interest to all research and industrial actors that attempt to develop and use reheat combustion systems.

3.1 QUALITATIVE FEATURES OF THE HYDROGEN REHEAT FLAMES

Figure 4 illustrates selected instantaneous features of the (statistically steady-state) stable hydrogen reheat flame corresponding to low firing-temperature conditions. The cross-sections marked as MD1-3 in Fig. 4(a), showing the spatial pattern of the hydrogen mass fraction, provide a qualitative representation of the spatially-evolving mixing process that takes place in the Mixing Duct region of the flow between the fuel and the oxidizer streams. The vortical flow structures responsible for the fast mixing process that takes place in the mixing duct are quite different for the inner and outer nozzles respectively. The inner nozzles are characterized by a higher mixing rate compared to the outer ones as evidenced in the figure. The cross-sections marked as CC1-6 in Fig. 4(a), showing the spatial pattern of the instantaneous fluid temperature, provide a qualitative representation of local and global features of the turbulent flame front. Evidently, the flame is predicted to anchor on the inner (lower in the figure) side of the combustion chamber, consistent with a faster spontaneous ignition process enhanced by a higher mixing rate and thus by the earlier increase in the temperature of the fuel-oxidizer mixture. This characteristic flame-anchoring behaviour, empirically observed in experimental testing, is also theoretically expected at the low firing-temperature conditions due to the lower temperature induced by the injection of secondary air on the outer (higher in the figure) side of the combustion chamber. Although a certain degree of spatial unsteadiness of the flame is observed, associated with the up- and downstream motion of the "free" unanchored branch of the reaction front, the absence of significant combustion dynamics confirms the soundness of the flame-stabilization strategy adopted in the CBB and based on the robust support to the spontaneous ignition process provided by the inner recirculation zone. Furthermore, it can be observed that a relatively cold, and hydrogen rich, fluid region is present in the CC1 cross section while an intensely-burning hotspot is clearly visible in the CC2 cross section, both likely resulting from imperfect mixing. The spatial pattern of the fluid temperature observed in the downstream cross sections CC3 to CC6 suggests that, even at low firing-temperature conditions, complete combustion of the hydrogen fuel is achieved in a relatively short distance within the combustion chamber whereas only very small parcels of fluid appear as unreacted.

Figure 4(b) focuses on the most upstream combustion chamber region (Zone I) and, showing the spatial pattern of the HO_2 radical mass fraction in cross sections CC1-4, provides a qualitative illustration of the flame stabilization process due to spontaneous ignition. Here, the HO_2 radical is considered as a precursor for autoignition and it is observed that, in cross section CC2, a uniform and relatively high mass-fraction value of this species is present in the unburnt reactants, corresponding to the fiercely burning flame visible in the homologous cross section of Fig 4(a). Conversely, the uneven HO_2 spatial pattern observed in

(a)

(b)

FIG. 4: INSTANTANEOUS FEATURES OF THE HYDROGEN REHEAT FLAME AT LOW FIRING-TEMPERATURE CONDITIONS. CROSS-SECTIONS OF THE MIXING DUCT (MD1-3) COLORED BY THE HYDROGEN MASS FRACTION AND OF THE COMBUSTION CHAMBER (CC1-6) COLORED BY THE TEMPERATURE (a). CROSS-SECTIONS OF THE COMBUSTION CHAMBER (CC1-4) COLORED BY THE HO₂ MASS FRACTION (b).

FIG. 5: TEMPORAL AVERAGE OF THE INSTANTANEOUS TEMPERATURE FIELD (a) AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE INSTANTANEOUS HEAT RELEASE RATE (b).

cross section CC1, characterized by generally lower values compared to CC2, suggests that, in the most upstream region of the combustion chamber, flame stabilization is not uniquely due to spontaneous ignition but a propagation component is also present due to the recirculation of hot combustion products.

3.2 MEAN FIELDS

The qualitative, instantaneous features of the hydrogen reheat flame that have been discussed in the previous section are confirmed by the mean quantities shown in Figs. 5 and 6. As illustrated by the mean temperature field in Fig. 5(a) and by the mean longitudinal velocity component in Fig. 6(a), the statistically steady-state flame is stabilized in the inner (lower) part of the combustion chamber by the presence of the hot recirculating combustion products, relatively low velocities and long residence times. The spatial pattern of the instantaneous heat-release rate standard deviation, shown in Fig. 5(b), evidences the moderate spatial unsteadiness of the outer portion of the reaction front that

is present at the low firing-temperature conditions. As explained in the previous section, such unsteadiness does not characterize the whole combustion process but is solely related to the up- and downstream displacement of the flame "free" branch along the outer wall of the combustion chamber.

Notably, as illustrated in Fig. 6(a), the mean longitudinal velocity field reveals a significant outward (upward) deflection of the high-speed flow exiting the mixing duct. This flow deflection is caused by the blockage effect that the flame stabilized in the recirculation region exerts on the approaching reactants flow, inhibiting ignition and flame stabilization within the most upstream region of the outer side of the combustion chamber.

Figure 6(b), showing the spatial distribution of mean hydrogen mass fraction, confirms the observation derived from the instantaneous fields about a sub-optimal mixing of the fuel emerging from the outermost fuel injection nozzle. This is a finding of crucial importance to the ongoing optimization of the CBB fuel-injection system and has already been addressed in the development work leading to a new and improved version of the

FIG. 6: TEMPORAL AVERAGES OF THE INSTANTANEOUS LONGITUDINAL VELOCITY COMPONENT (a) AND HYDROGEN MASS FRACTION (b).

CBB.

The scatter plots in Fig. 7, comparing the distribution of the mean HO_2 -radical mass fraction in progress-variable space at the CC1 and CC2 cross-sectional locations illustrated in Fig. 4, highlights the spatial evolution of the mean flame structure in the longitudinal direction. Here, the reaction progress variable C is defined as a scalar parametrization of the reactive flow field that is equal to zero in the fresh reactants ($C = 0$) and unity in the fully burnt products ($C = 1$) where, in the present analysis, C is based on the fluid temperature. As evidenced by the figure, the flame structure and the downstream location (CC2) is characterized by generally higher values of the HO_2 mass fraction, a precursor and marker of spontaneous-ignition conditions, across the whole progress-variable range. Crucially, the occurrence of significantly higher HO_2 concentrations in correspondence of the preheat layer, at progress variable values between 0.3 and 0.5, suggests that the flame at the downstream location (CC2) is more strongly controlled by spontaneous ignition compared to the flame at the upstream location (CC1). There, on the

contrary, a lower prevalence of HO_2 in the preheat layer of the mean flame structure, and a thinner scatter distribution skewed to higher progress-variable values, suggests an important deflagration component at the upstream location (CC1).

3.3 TRANSITION TO HIGH-TEMPERATURE FIRING

The transition to the high-temperature firing conditions is implemented via a stepwise increment of the hydrogen fuel mass-flow rate over a time period corresponding to $7 \times t_{res}^{CBB}$, as described in Sec. 2.2 above. The increased mass-flow rate of the fuel causes a gradual upstream displacement of the "free" branch of the reaction front that is located in the outer part of the combustion chamber. This, in turn, causes a change in the global flame morphology inducing a transition from an S-shaped flame, mainly stabilized in the inner (lower) region of the combustion chamber, to a V-shaped flame stabilized on both the inner and the outer side of it. Figure 8 illustrate the changes in the flame morphology and stabilization location that take place during the

FIG. 7: SCATTER PLOTS OF THE MEAN HO₂-RADICAL MASS FRACTION VS TEMPERATURE-BASED PROGRESS VARIABLE. THE SYMBOLS ARE COLORED BY THE MEAN HEAT-RELEASE RATE.

transition from low- to high-temperature firing conditions. The upstream displacement of the flame front on the outer side of the combustion chamber is fairly evident while, careful comparison of the flame-stabilization locations on the inner side of the combustion chamber, also reveals the flame presence slightly upstream of the inner corner of the mixing duct. Note that the shape of the mixing duct prevents, for the selected boundary conditions, further upstream propagation of the flame along the mixing-duct wall and towards the fuel injectors. Furthermore, a region of locally very high fluid temperature is clearly observed immediately downstream of the dark blue iso-contour line that marks the hydrogen mass fraction corresponding to the target high-temperature firing conditions. Before concluding the present section, it is important to emphasize that, in the present numerical study, only the transient process, representing the transition from low to high-temperature firing conditions, is investigated by a gradual increase of the amount of hydrogen injected.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The complex and interdependent physical processes of in-line fuel injection, its mixing with the oxidizer and its spontaneous ignition, controlling flame stabilization and morphology in a realistic Constant Pressure Sequential Combustion system, are studied with a series of Large Eddy Simulations (LES). The calculations are performed on a geometrically accurate represen-

tation of Ansaldo Energia's GT36 Constant Pressure Sequential Combustor (CPSC), originally designed for natural-gas firing of the gas turbine. The numerical simulations reported here are therefore exploring operating conditions significantly outside of the originally-intended fuel characteristics for this burner geometry. In particular, the LES calculations have shown the ability to capture important mixing effects that are coupled with the process of spontaneous ignition in the flame stabilization process, highlighting how the system is able to provide proper flame anchoring and fuel burnout at low firing-temperature conditions. The LES predictions also capture the upstream displacement of the flame front and spatial changes in the heat release pattern caused by higher firing temperatures. Further work will consider a more detailed analysis of the high firing-temperature conditions and a modification of the fuel injection and mixing duct configuration to improve the spatial distribution of the hydrogen fraction in the crucial flow region located immediately upstream of the desired flame stabilization position.

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FIG. 8: INSTANTANEOUS TEMPERATURE FIELDS ILLUSTRATING THE FLAME MORPHOLOGY AND LOCATION FOR LOW- (a) AND HIGH-TEMPERATURE (b) FIRING CONDITIONS. THE DARK BLUE ISO-CONTOUR LINE REPRESENTS THE HYDROGEN MASS FRACTION CORRESPONDING TO NOMINAL ADIABATIC FLAME TEMPERATURE AT THE HIGH-TEMPERATURE FIRING CONDITIONS.

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